

Report on 2020 plant pest survey activities

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At the request of the European Commission, EFSA was asked to support the EU Member States in the preparation and planning of the surveys of the EU quarantine pests (EFSA mandates on plant pest surveillance M-2017-0137 and M-2020-0114).

In response, EFSA developed a toolkit that consists of three pest-specific guidelines, pest survey cards on quarantine organisms, as well as general survey guidelines and a statistical tool (i.e. RiBESS+). The aim of the pest survey cards is to guide the EU Member States in the preparation of plant pest surveys by providing relevant information on the pests for this activity. The aim of the guidelines is to assist the EU Member States in the design of statistically sound and risk-based surveys for quarantine pests.

The purpose of the current document is to facilitate the access to and to list all the outputs and materials delivered in 2020 in the context of both mentioned mandates. The listed outputs are delivered in different formats and platforms: i.e. PDF files in the EFSA Journal, StoryMaps in the ESRI Plant Pest Survey Cards Gallery, videos in the EFSA YouTube Channel and shared presentations at different forums, webinars and online courses. All outputs in response to the mandate M-2017-0137 were delivered, as well as the first outputs of M-2020-0114. The activities of 2021-2026 will be focussed on the delivery of the outputs for the latter mandate.

Within the Plant Health team of the ALPHA unit, the following persons contributed to the preparation and delivery of the outputs: Giulia Mattion, Alice Delbianco, Ignazio Graziosi and Sybren Vos. In addition, Mart Kinkar was involved in the coordination and preparation of the pest survey cards until February 2020, Sara Tramontini prepared two pest survey cards and Maria Chiara Rosace produced the pest survey cards on the ESRI ArcGIS StoryMaps platform.

EFSA Surveillance outputs were promoted through the EFSA Plant Health Team Twitter account (@Plants_EFSA), gaining an average of about 5000 visualizations per Tweet.

Table 1 shows the outputs published in 2020.

Table 2 shows the events which the plant pest surveillance project has organised or collaborated with in 2020.

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Table 1: Outputs on plant pest surveillance published in 2020

	Outputs	Publication date	Mandate number	Link to the output
Event reports	Cooperation in crisis preparedness for <i>Agrilus planipennis</i> in the European Union	10 December	M-2017-0137	https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2020.EN-1985
	Workshops report for cooperation in crisis preparedness for <i>Phyllosticta citricarpa</i> in the European Union	10 December	M-2017-0137	https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2020.EN-1984
Guidelines	General guidelines for statistically sound and risk-based surveys of plant pests	8 September	M-2017-0137	https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2020.EN-1919
	Guidelines for statistically sound and risk-based surveys of <i>Agrilus planipennis</i>	17 December	M-2017-0137	https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2020.EN-1983
	Guidelines for statistically sound and risk-based surveys of <i>Phyllosticta citricarpa</i>	8 July	M-2017-0137	https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2020.EN-1893
	Guidelines for statistically sound and risk-based surveys of <i>Xylella fastidiosa</i>	8 June	M-2017-0137	https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2020.EN-1873
RiBESS+¹	Tutorial video	6 October	M-2017-0137	https://youtu.be/qYHqCiMxqDY
Pest survey cards	<i>Anthonomus eugenii</i>	22 June	M-2017-0137	https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2020.EN-1887
	<i>Agrilus planipennis</i>	16 November	M-2017-0137	https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2020.EN-1945
	<i>Conotrachelus nenuphar</i>	16 December	M-2020-0114	https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2020.EN-1989
	Flavescence dorée phytoplasma and its vector <i>Scaphoideus titanus</i>	10 August	M-2017-0137	https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2020.EN-1909
	<i>Fusarium circinatum</i>	6 May	M-2017-0137	https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2020.EN-1842
	<i>Geosmithia morbida</i> and its vector <i>Pityophthorus juglandis</i>	7 July	M-2017-0137	https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2020.EN-1894
	<i>Pantoea stewartii</i> subsp. <i>stewartii</i>	12 June	M-2017-0137	https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2020.EN-1878
	<i>Phyllosticta citricarpa</i>	9 June	M-2017-0137	https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2020.EN-1863
	<i>Pissodes cibriani</i> , <i>P. fasciatus</i> , <i>P. nemorensis</i> , <i>P. nitidus</i> , <i>P. punctatus</i> , <i>P. strobi</i> , <i>P. terminalis</i> , <i>P. yunnanensis</i> and <i>P. zitacuarensis</i>	10 August	M-2017-0137	https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2020.EN-1910
	<i>Pomacea</i> spp.	12 June	M-2017-0137	https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2020.EN-1877
	<i>Pseudomonas syringae</i> pv. <i>actinidiae</i>	9 December	M-2017-0137	https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2020.EN-1986
	<i>Rhagoletis fausta</i>	28 August	M-2017-0137	https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2020.EN-1917
	<i>Rhagoletis pomonella</i>	3 August	M-2017-0137	https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2020.EN-1908

¹ RiBESS+ is freely available prior registration at: <https://r4eu.efsa.europa.eu/app/ribess>

	<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>	8 July	M-2017-0137	https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2020.EN-1895
	<i>Thaumatotibia leucotreta</i>	28 August	M-2017-0137	https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2020.EN-1916
	<i>Thekopsora minima</i>	28 August	M-2017-0137	https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2020.EN-1915
	Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus	29 July	M-2017-0137	https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2020.EN-1904
	<i>Xylosandrus crassiusculus</i>	29 July	M-2017-0137	https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2020.EN-1903
Story maps	<i>Agrilus anxius</i>	25 March	M-2017-0137	https://arcq.is/L8nG50
	<i>Agrilus auroguttatus</i>	25 March	M-2017-0137	https://arcq.is/15PuCq
	<i>Aleurocanthus spiniferus</i> , <i>A. woglumi</i> and <i>A. citriperdus</i>	18 June	M-2017-0137	https://arcq.is/u5DTL
	<i>Anoplophora chinensis</i>	24 March	M-2017-0137	https://arcq.is/19HTyn
	<i>Anoplophora glabripennis</i>	25 March	M-2017-0137	https://arcq.is/KOCb9
	<i>Aromia bungii</i>	5 May	M-2017-0137	https://arcq.is/1r09uO
	<i>Bactrocera dorsalis</i>	5 May	M-2017-0137	https://arcq.is/0aXqST
	<i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i>	26 March	M-2017-0137	https://arcq.is/1SHunJ
	<i>Candidatus liberibacter solanacearum</i> and its vectors	18 June	M-2017-0137	https://arcq.is/0bqWC8
	<i>Ceratitis rosa</i>	24 September	M-2017-0137	https://arcq.is/S91be0
	Citrus tristeza virus	25 May	M-2017-0137	https://arcq.is/0gae9O
	<i>Clavibacter sepedonicus</i>	8 September	M-2017-0137	https://arcq.is/1znCCn0
	<i>Dendrolimus sibiricus</i>	25 March	M-2017-0137	https://arcq.is/1WWyeD
	<i>Epitrix cucumeris</i> , <i>E. papa</i> , <i>E. subcrinita</i> and <i>E. tuberis</i>	8 September	M-2017-0137	https://arcq.is/H5fO8
	<i>Globodera rostochiensis</i> and <i>G. palida</i>	8 September	M-2017-0137	https://arcq.is/1iXik4
	Huanglongbing and its vectors	18 June	M-2017-0137	https://arcq.is/15nPKn
	<i>Meloidogyne chitwoodii</i> and <i>M. fallax</i>	8 September	M-2017-0137	https://arcq.is/08m44b
	Non-European <i>Monochamus</i> spp.	26 March	M-2017-0137	https://arcq.is/1bf9W8
	<i>Polygraphus proximus</i>	26 March	M-2017-0137	https://arcq.is/0airLW
	<i>Popillia japonica</i>	26 March	M-2017-0137	https://arcq.is/1HbK9q0
	<i>Ralstonia solanacearum</i>	31 July	M-2017-0137	https://arcq.is/1b8e95
	Rose rosette virus	26 March	M-2017-0137	https://arcq.is/144zje
	<i>Scirtothrips aurantii</i> , <i>S. citri</i> and <i>S. dorsalis</i>	24 September	M-2017-0137	https://arcq.is/1KS8GG2
	<i>Synchytrium endobioticum</i>	14 July	M-2017-0137	https://arcq.is/qeSWC
	<i>Tecia solanivora</i>	29 June	M-2017-0137	https://arcq.is/1SHLzK
	<i>Toxoptera citricida</i>	22 May	M-2017-0137	https://arcq.is/1DCjzX
	<i>Xanthomonas citri</i> pv. <i>citri</i> and pv. <i>aurantifolii</i>	22 June	M-2017-0137	https://arcq.is/1uvaf0
	<i>Xylella fastidiosa</i>	8 September	M-2017-0137	https://arcq.is/09m4r1

Table 2: Events which the plant pest surveillance project has organised or collaborated with in 2020

	Event	Date	Organiser	People involved	Available material
EFSA sessions	PLH open plenary	8-10 July	EFSA	Speakers: Stephen Parnell, Sybren Vos Co-organisers: Giulia Mattion, Maria Chiara Rosace	https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/events/event/88th-plh-plenary-meeting-open-observers
	Network meeting	2-3 December	EFSA	Speakers: Alice Delbianco, Ignazio Graziosi, Giulia Mattion, Stephen Parnell, Sybren Vos	https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/events/event/16th-meeting-efsa-scientific-network-risk-assessment-plant-health
Chief Plant Health Officers (COPHs) meeting	Toolkit for plant pest surveillance	19 October	EC	Speaker: Sybren Vos	http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4560240
Trainings	Course for phytosanitary inspectors	5 November	NPPO Lombardia	Speakers: Ignazio Graziosi, Giulia Mattion, Sybren Vos	http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4561768
	CIHEAM-IAMZ	14-16 December	CIHEAM, EFSA	Speakers: Ignazio Graziosi, Elena Lázaro, Sybren Vos	http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4561786
Webinars	EFSA Toolkit for <i>Xylella fastidiosa</i> surveys	6 July	XF-Actors project, EFSA	Speakers: Elena Lázaro, Sybren Vos Dispatcher: Giulia Mattion Q&A team: José Cortiñas Abrahantes, Stephen Parnell, Martijn Schenk, Antonio Vicent Civera	https://www.xfactorsproject.eu/event/efsa-toolkit-for-xylella-fastidiosa-surveys-webinar/
	Toolkit for plant pest surveillance	6 October	EFSA	Speakers: Ignazio Graziosi, Sybren Vos Dispatcher: Giulia Mattion Q&A team: José Cortiñas Abrahantes, Stephen Parnell	https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/events/event/webinar-toolkit-plant-pest-surveillance
	Detect your pests: practical statistical framework for risk-based surveillance	21 October	EFSA	Speakers: Elena Lázaro, Sybren Vos Dispatcher: Giulia Mattion Q&A team: Stephen Parnell, Antonio Vicent Civera	https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/events/event/webinar-detect-your-pests-practical-statistical-framework-risk-based

	Pest surveys following an outbreak: delimiting and buffer zone surveys	1 December	EFSA	<p>Speakers: Ignazio Graziosi, Stephen Parnell</p> <p>Dispatcher: Giulia Mattion</p> <p>Q&A team: Antonio Vicent Civera, Sybren Vos</p>	https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/events/event/webinar-pest-surveys-following-outbreak-delimiting-and-buffer-zone
Working groups meetings	Pest survey cards review and pest survey methodology	2020	EFSA	EFSA Working group on Pest Survey	https://www.efsa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/wg/plant-health/wg-plh-Pest-Survey.pdf
Workshops	Cooperation in crisis preparedness for <i>Agilus planipennis</i> in the European Union	14-16 September	Estonian Agricultural Board, EFSA	<p>PLH: Ignazio Graziosi, Maria Rosaria Mannino, Giulia Mattion, Sybren Vos</p> <p>Grant holder: Birger Ilau, Mart Kinkar, Ülle Metsman, Rob Tanner</p> <p>EFSA Working group on Pest Survey</p>	https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2020.EN-1985